

Implications of plant-to-plant variability on spatial variability of yield in vegetable crops

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Abstract

Plant population and environment vary spatially within crops and determine yield potential. Optimising management to account for the effect these factors have on yield potential could improve production outcomes. Under optimal conditions spatial variability in established population and interplant variability drives within-field yield variability. Here we obtain a measure of intra-plant and population variability in a field of onions, and develop a novel approach to define management zones within the field based on population and environment effects on yield potential.

Plant spacing and individual bulb weight of c. 2000 onion plants were measured across four different areas of a field with optimal growth. Density distributions were fitted to bulb weight and plant spacing. In addition, 104 point samples (1.8m²) were collected as a grid to determine spatial variability of yield and population. From the distribution functions, the range of yield and population under optimal growth was determined.

Potential yield was 92 tha⁻¹ at 59.8 plants m⁻². Bulb mass was distributed normally (154g ± 49g) and based on this variability, optimal yield ranges are above 83 tha⁻¹. Yields below 60 tha⁻¹ were defined as severely growth limited at the standard population. Expected population range was 54–78 plants m⁻². We combined these layers to develop a management zone map. This approach identifies areas in the field where tactical in-season management can improve yield of growth limited areas, or where longer term strategic management is needed to optimise future plant establishment and population to improve overall outcomes.

Background

The spatial variability of crop yield within a field offers scope for improved economic and sustainability outcomes, if the appropriate management can be actioned in the right zones of the field.

Consequently, there has been a substantial amount of work seeking to define management zones (MZ, e.g. see Nawar et al. (2017) for a review). Spatial measures of soil characteristics alone are not sufficient to delineate a management zone, but crop characteristics are also needed, as crop growth is a result of integration of the various stresses experienced by the crop. Robertson et al., (2006; 2007) showed that zoning can be achieved if based on yield performance.

The yield at any sampling point in time within the field will depend on the crop variety, population, weather, management and the stresses experienced by the crop to that point in time. Ideally, management will eliminate stresses affecting growth, so that yield is at full potential and only limited by population, weather and genetics. An assumption for potential yield being similar in different sample points is that population does not vary across the field to the extent that yield levels might be affected, and that plant-to-plant variability is similar in each area, so that average plant weight is similar in each sample area.

However, for many crops, particularly many vegetable crops these assumptions do not hold. There is significant point-to-point variation in crop population reported for some vegetable crops (Boiffin et al. 1992; Reid & English 2000; Stibbe & Märlander 2002) which can be large enough to affect interpretation of management on yield (Reid & English 2000). This variation can be due to machinery issues, soil structure or moisture content. At the same time there is significant plant-to-plant variation in plant growth rate and final weight which can also affect interpretation of management responses from samples across the field (Reid & English 2000; Searle et al. 2014). This means that for a crop growing under uniform and non-limiting growth conditions, there will be a range of possible potential yields at different sampling points in the field depending on what the individual plant weight values are and the number of plants in the sample.

Based on the variability of plant population and intra-plant variability across, we have developed the concept of management action zones. In simple terms if the measured yield is below the potential range then some in-season management can be implemented; if the population is below the targeted range and has affected yield then strategic management to improve population for a subsequent crop needs to be implemented. If both population and yield are below the optimum then decisions about in-season tactical and strategic decision need to be made. For areas where both yield and population are within the optimum range then no additional management needs to be implemented to increase yields. These four options are summarised in Table 1.

To develop this approach we need to know something about the plant-to-plant and population variability. Here we report on work as part of a project aimed at better spatial management of onion crops, where we measure inter-plant and population variability weight, so that the potential range and a lower limit of range can be determined, and the development of MAZ in a field is evaluated. Subsequent work on using sensors to identify MAZ early in the season and evaluating outcomes by changing management practices will be reported separately.

Methods

Onion seed of cultivar 'Rhinestone' was planted on 2 August 2015 into a silt loam soil at the LandWISE Microfarm, Hawke's Bay, New Zealand (<http://microfarm.landwise.org.nz/>). Plant spacing was targeted at 7.2cm within a row, with eight rows per bed. Bed width was 1.8m. The soil had good fertility (pH =6.2±0.25, Olsen P=67±8.4 mg/L, K=2±0.20 me/100g, mineral N to 60 cm. depth=279±69.1 kg N/ha). The crop was managed with standard commercial practice and input from a group of producers, to ensure that there were no limitations to growth and the crop grew and yielded at potential.

Individual plant spacing and date of emergence were recorded for c. 2000 onion plants across four different areas of a field with optimal growth. At eight different stages during growth an area of 0.9m² (a 0.5 m length of one bed) was harvested from each of the four areas, and individual plant weight and leaf area recorded for analysis of plant variance over time. Final yield was recorded from the onions from 1.8 m² plot (a 1 m length of a bed) in each of the four areas, c. 450 plants in total. At lifting time, each of these onions was individually lifted and tagged. Following commercial lifting of the remainder of the field, the tagged onions were placed back into the field for curing. After curing and final harvesting, bulb weights were individually recorded. Density distributions were fitted to bulb weight and plant spacing with mean and standard deviation used to calculate the coefficient of variation (CV). The contributions of emergence date, spacing and growth to variance in bulb weight over time and at harvest was analysed by with a mixed model using the rptR package in R to see how much of the variation in final bulb weight was set or could be managed.

At final harvest 99 point samples (1.8m²) were collected as a grid across the field to determine spatial variability of yield and population. These were collected every 20 m along the length of a bed and from every other bed. Onions were lifted by hand from each of the sample areas and placed in bare margins of the field to dry down, and then bulb counts and weights were recorded.

Table 1. Management action zones (MAZ) for different areas of a field based on yield and population being within a potential range. The MAZ defines areas in the field that may respond to management and improve outcomes. It also defines the type of management that may be needed — tactical, within-season management or strategic system management.

Management Action Zone	Yield within potential	Yield below potential
Population expected	MAZ 1 No management needed	MAZ 3 Revise management (tactical management)
Population below expected	MAZ 2 Increase population (strategic management)	MAZ 4 Increase population and growth (review tactical and strategic management)

To get an indication of variability in plant weight at a commercial scale, individual bulbs from 1.8m² areas were collected from four different areas in six commercial fields over two seasons. Distributions were fitted to estimate mean and standard deviation, and CV calculated. Individual plant spacings were measured in three replicate plots of six commercial fields.

Results

Emergence was relatively rapid for onions with 98% of plants appearing over a 10 day period. Almost all other plants appeared within 18 days, only one plant emerged later at 35 days from the start of emergence. Bulb weight was reduced by time of emergence, but only for plants emerging more than 12 days after emergence started. In the four plots where growth was not limited, the yield was 92 tha⁻¹. Bulb mass was distributed normally (154 ± 49 g, CV of 32%) and, based on this variability, the optimal yield ranges are above 83 tha⁻¹. The mixed model analysis indicated that 8% of the variation in bulb weight was due to plant space and neighbour size effects and 31% was due to the spread of emergence. The remaining 61% of variation was due to differences between plants in growth rate and competition during growth. The CV of bulb weight from commercial fields ranged from 30 to 70%, with the higher variation associated with lower yields, the smaller CV associated with higher yields.

Average plant spacing was 7.4 ± 3.6 cm (CV of 49%) with an average population of 59.8 plants m⁻². With this amount of variability in spacing it would be expected that the population in any given are of 1 m² would range from 53 to 69 plants. Results from commercial fields show that the CV% of between plant spacing ranged from 46 to 67%, with five of the six fields having CV over 56%.

Final harvest across the grid sample points of the field ranged from 41 to 107 tha⁻¹ and averaged 70 tha⁻¹. The sample yields are mapped as a grid in Figure 1. From the bulb weight distribution values, we took optimum yields to be above 83 tha⁻¹ and we arbitrarily assigned three other yield zones, 70–83, 60–70 and less than 60 tha⁻¹. When mapped this way, 16% of the field area is within the potential yield range. These yield results suggest that management could be implemented across the remaining 84% of the field to increase yields.

Figure 1. Spatial variability in onion yields (tha⁻¹) at harvest at the Microfarm field for the 2016–17 growing season. Gridded samples were collected for yield assessment across the field at final harvest. Zones were based on yields – above the potential range of 83 tha⁻¹, 71-82 tha⁻¹, 61-70 tha⁻¹ and less than 60 tha⁻¹. Yields at each sample point are recorded.

We identified MAZ values for each grid by comparing yield and population in each grid to the lower potential yield limit (83 tha⁻¹) and the lower limit of the target population (53 plants m⁻²) estimated given the variability found in bulb weight and plant spacing. These values are mapped in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Spatial variability in management action zones (MAZ) for an onion crop grown in the Microfarm field for the 2016–17 growing season. MAZ values are given for each point of the field, meanings of values are indicated in Table 1.

When using this approach, 57% of the field is in MAZ 1, indicating that no management is needed to increase yields. Of the remainder of the field, only 11% is in MAZ 3 – where in-season management could be used to improve outcomes. This is a much lower proportion of the field where management could possibly improve outcomes compared to the indication that 84% of the field would respond to management based on results from the yield map (Figure 1). Based on the proportion of the field in MAZ 2 and 4, yield was limited by population in up to 31% of the field.

Discussion

A MAZ is a novel approach to mapping a field for spatial management and defines if yield is limited by poor plant growth or if it is limited by population, or both. As such it provides an indication of the type of management that could improve outcomes. For the field in this study, based on yield alone, approximately 84% of the field was below a potential yield limit and likely to respond to some extent to spatial management. However, when the yield and population were considered in relation to optimal values then the MAZ approach indicated that only 11% would respond to in-season management to increase yield, a substantial difference. This indicates that plant spacing and the intra-plant variability in growth should be taken into account when considering spatial zoning for management of onions.

Plant spacing of vegetable crops is quite variable (Siemens & Gayler 2015) and can have a CV over 75%. Using a calibrated sower, the right seed and planting into the right soil conditions are important for reducing the variability. The CV of 41% for the onion spacing in this study is at the lower end of the range of commercial fields we surveyed and indicates good planting practice. We have implemented MAZ estimates using this variability to calculate target population range. While in practice the spacing variability might be higher, using a CV of 41% as the base means that the cost of practices that result in poor plant population can be estimated from MAZ maps.

The plant-to-plant variability used to estimate if yield is within a potential range is a CV of 32%. Compared to surveyed fields, this is at the low end of variability. The contribution of different factors to the variability of onion bulb weight indicates that there is little within-season management that could reduce this variability. Emergence spread of the onions may be one way of reducing the plant-to-plant variability, but for this crop, it was only the plant emerging after 12 days that increased the variability. For the onions in this field, the spread of emergence was good compared to standard practices (Searle et al. 2014). Thus, it can be suggested that a CV of 31% be used to estimate if a crop is within the potential yield range or not.

The MAZ map presented here is based on potential yield estimates and as such is retrospective. Future implementations will use sensors to estimate canopy growth in relation to a potential range. The potential growth and yield can be estimated with crop models, but the between-plant variability will determine what the potential growth limits are. Early identification of MAZ during the crop growth will enable management decisions to be made for implementation in-season.

While the MAZ gives an overview of the type of management that can be applied in each zone (Table 1), it does not solve the question of exactly what management needs to be applied. Sensors could be added to this approach to determine if N might be needed, or if N could be reduced in areas that are population limited or already at potential. Future work will evaluate these questions to improve yield and sustainability outcomes.

Our results show that the MAZ approach provides a novel way of delineating zones in the field where management can be actioned in-season or where longer term strategic management is needed to improve overall outcomes. While we have developed this approach with onions, it is likely that it can be applied to other crops, in particular where there is considerable plant-to-plant variability.

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References

- Boiffin J, Durr C, Fleury A, Marin-Lafleche A, Maillet I 1992. Analysis of the variability of sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L) growth during the early stages. I. Influence of various conditions on crop establishment. *Agronomie* 12(7): 515–525.
- Nawar S, Corstanje R, Halcro G, Mulla D, Mouazen AM 2017. Chapter four-delineation of soil management zones for variable-rate fertilization: A Review. *Advances in Agronomy* 143: 175–245.
- Reid J, English J 2000. Potential yield in carrots (*Daucus carota* L.): theory, test, and an application. *Annals of botany* 85(5): 593–605.
- Robertson M, Isbister B, Maling I, Oliver Y, Wong M, Adams M, Bowden J, Tozer P 2006. Managing spatial and seasonal variability within field can improve the profitability of WA grain production. *Proceedings 13th Australian Society of Agronomy*. Pp. 10–14.
- Robertson M, Isbister B, Maling I, Oliver Y, Wong M, Adams M, Bowden B, Tozer P 2007. Opportunities and constraints for managing within-field spatial variability in Western Australian grain production. *Field Crops Research* 104(1): 60–67.
- Searle B, Johnstone P, Reid J 2014. Aspects of production affecting variability in vegetable crop quality. *Acta Horticulturae* 1123: 17–26.
- Siemens MC, Gayler RR 2015. Improving seed spacing uniformity of precision vegetable planters. *Applied Agricultural Engineering* 32(5): 579–587.
- Stibbe C, Märlander B 2002. Field emergence dynamics significance to intraspecific competition and growth efficiency in sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.). *European journal of agronomy* 17(3): 161–171.